

The extent to Which Faculty Members in Jordanian Universities Accept The E-Learning Approach During Corona Pandemic

Nidal ZakiAmarin, Tarik Faris Al Soub

Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<p><i>One of the challenges that faces implementing technologies in education and reflects on the process of teaching and learning, since it relates to the two main parts in the educational process (Teaches and Students). And their new role which is fully different from their traditional role before corona pandemic. The students used to be a passive learner and the teacher used to be the main source of information. While in this exceptional era there was a radical change in everything, especially in education, the student became the core of the learning process and the teacher became a guide. The purpose of this study was to examine the factors that faculty members in Jordanian Universities accept the e-Learning approach during corona pandemic. Research questions examined were (a) To what extent the eLearning approach improves the learning process from Jordanian University teaching staff perspectives? (b) To what extent do university teaching staff members accept e-learning approaches in light of corona pandemic? (c) Do University teaching staff members acceptance of e-learning approach in the light of Corona pandemic system differs according to (gender, age, academic rank, and years of experience? The decomposed theory of planned behavior was used as theoretical framework.</i></p>
Received: March 14, 2021	<p><i>A survey questionnaire was adapted. Participants were faculty members in Jordanian Universities. Data from 372 participants were analyzed using descriptive and multiple regression methods. Findings showed that faculty members agreed that e-learning approach improves eLearning process.</i></p>
Accepted: May 10, 2021	<p><i>Regarding the predictors of faculty members' behavioral intention to accept the eLearning approaches were: attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control were significant predictors. Faculty members' comments suggested that lack of equipment, lack of training, lack of funding, security issues, and firewalls were possible obstacles affecting perceived usefulness and compatibility</i></p>
Keywords	
E-Learning approachteaching staff, Quality, Computer- Assisted Learning (CAL).	
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4747321	

Introduction

The Corona pandemic imposed on most countries of the world to introduce e-learning as a teaching method in the learning and teaching process in international universities. Computer learning development (CAL) is related to developing distance learning through internet connection. (Hubenova, Kashamova,2020), the Jordanian Ministry of Higher Education urged Jordanian universities to take more serious measures to implement distance learning and education via the Internet, as well as many educational strategies to ensure the quality of education. (Akour& others, 2020). What the education system has become vulnerable to external influences and dangers (Bozkurt & Sharma, 2020). Universities 'reliance on distance learning stems from their desire to direct their actions towards local and global practices and policies to overcome the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic as they responded to the rapid digital transformation of their educational activities without looking at the universities' economic.

The COVID-19 virus has posed many challenges and tremendous pressures on humanity, turning education in universities to e-learning as a way of communicating and distributing information in all different educational settings to students. This increases the pressure on faculty members to increase their productivity and change educational strategies to accommodate the educational changes and reforms related to this epidemic, thus generating a new vision and new roles for faculty members in the e-learning environment, as many universities have searched for new programs as an educational method for teaching educational materials through education. Study (Akour& others, 2020) showed that most teachers have moderate to high motivation for the distance they

teach. Communication with family was the most reported self-coping activity. University professors demonstrated different levels of psychological distress and challenges while implementing national precautionary measures in the battle against COVID-19 during the teaching process.study (Adedoyin,O and Soykan,E.(2020)). indicated that the online learning differs from distance teaching in epidemic situations, online learning will be more sustainable while educational activities will become more hybrid, provided that the challenges encountered during this epidemic are well explored and turned into opportunities.The degree of readiness of universities with all its components works on the success of e-learning, in addition to the desire of faculty members and the range of their skills and competencies necessary to teach students in the e-learning method, which increases the level of learning, (Arnaud, 2020).

Concept of eLearning

Wikipedia. (2018,) defines eLearning as an interactive approach of students that provides learner with the use of communication and information technologies, and it depends on an integrated digital electronic environment that displays courses through electronic networks, and this environment provides ways of guidance and counseling, organizing tests, as well as managing resources The importance of e-learning lies in solving the problem of knowledge explosion and increasing demand for knowledge and chances of acceptance in education, in addition to the ease of training and teaching workers without the need to leave their work, and contribute to break psychological barriers between teacher and learner, as well as satisfying needs and characteristics of learner with Increase return on investment by reducing education. cost Shomak et al. (2011.) define an eLearning approach as a system that provides the necessary services to deal with all aspects of course administration through a single, consistent web interface. Rodrigues et al. (2019). define e-learning as “an innovative web-based system mainly computer technologies and other forms of CRL whose main aim is to provide learners with a personalized, learner-centered, open enjoyable, and interactive learning environment supporting and enhancing the learning processes (p. 95)”.

Problem statement

E-learning approach is considered as new revolution in learning process. E- learning process carried out through using new communication means such as computer, networks and multimedia, including sound, image, graphics, electronic libraries, as well as the Internet. Although e- learning process growth was very low due to many aspects; during the year 2020 and because of Corona Pandemic, many teaching institutions regardless of their level have applied different types of eLearning. Nowadays almost all teaching institutions are using the mechanism in delivering the information to their students. Based on the problem statement is to answer the following questions:

Q1- To what extent eLearning approach improves the learning process from Jordanian Universities teaching staff Perspectives?

Q2- To what extent do universities teaching staff members accept eLearning approach in light of Corona pandemic?

Q3- Do Universities teaching staff members' acceptance of eLearning approach in the light of Corona pandemic approach differs according to (gender, age, academic rank, and years of experience)?

Study Significance:

The importance of this study stems from its topic importance, because e- learning has become an important issue for teaching institutions in all world countries. Such importance increased in the last year because of COVID 19 which caused all teaching institution to use e- learning approach due to implementation of lockdowns measures to prevent COVID 19 spread.

Study Objectives:

The study main objective is to identify the extent to which Faculty Members in Jordanian Universities Accept the eLearning Approach During Corona Pandemic

The study also aims to:

1-Identify the impact of eLearning on improving learning process from universities staff teaching perspective.

2- To find out if there are significant differences in universities teaching staff acceptance due to demographic variables.

Advantages, disadvantages and obstacles of eLearning

E-learning compared with traditional education has many advantages, the most important of which is flexibility in determining the appropriate time and place, and it provides advantage of sending and exchanging files between teacher and student in easier and faster ways. E-learning provides the possibility of conducting computerized tests (Halas, 2018) De-Marcos et al. (2016) reported that e-learning is an effective educational

platform. Nur, et al (2014) study concluded that sample's subjects preferred to learn via e-Learning due to its flexibility.

Titie, et al., (2018) indicated that the selected patterns of content and design were effective in mathematics. Benaichi and Benaichi (2018), concluded that advantages of using e-learning in the university from faculty teaching staff members is that e-learning approach has desirable features for university students and provides an appropriate environment for student use. Algahtani, (2013) identified some of e learning advantages such as e-learning flexibility in terms of time and place. It provides students with an access to huge amount of information. It enhances and establishing relations opportunities between learners and eliminating barriers that hinder some learners from participation due to fear of talking with others. He added that e- learning is cost effective due avoiding students need to travel and provide them with the chances to obtain the required information in any place.

Nur, et al (2014) indicated that one of the disadvantages of using e-Learning is it reduces face to face interaction between students. Benaichi and Benaichi (2018), reported that the disadvantages of eLearning in the university is the long sitting hours in front of a computer, which causes many diseases, and reduces the burden of teachers, and increases the burden. Benaichi and Benaichi (2018), reported that the disadvantages of e-learning in the university is the long sitting hours in front of a computer, which causes many diseases, and reduces the burden of teachers, and increases the burden. Al-Mazari (2014) reported that lack of technical support forms d the most important disadvantages.

Al-Hawamdeh (2011) found that the use of e-learning, has obstacles related to administrative and material aspects and obstacles related to e-learning itself in addition to obstacles related to teacher and the student Al-Hajaya (2010) concluded that the most important obstacles facing (faculty members In the sample universities is the infrastructure,.Tshabalala der van &NdereyaNydeya (2014). concluded that there are barriers that teaching staff face represented by learner perceptions related to eLearning policy, lack of top management support, lack of student's competencies and lecturers in using computers, as well as computers shortages. Randy (2011) reported that, many schools lack necessary e-learning equipment. He added that students also lack skills in computer literacy and self-motivation.

Universities Teaching Staff Acceptance of eLearning

Many local studies were conducted in this regard. Mazroua (2013) study aimed at identifying the trends of members of the Authority Teaching at King Khalid University towards the use of the electronic learning management system (blackboard) and its impact on some personal and organizational variables on their attitudes and the most important obstacles that limit using an eLearning management system. The study was that the attitudes of faculty members at King Khalid University towards the use of an electronic learning management system is moderately positive Suleiman (2014) conducted a study aimed at training faculty members at Taibah University on Using the learning management system and electronic content and its information awareness and knowledge Its effectiveness in developing e-learning skills and their information awareness. The research results indicate that faculty members 'lack of information Knowledge, e-learning skills, awareness of them and the effectiveness of e-training on the use of learning management system, and electronic content in developing the achievement of all cognitive aspects. In this regard Badawi (2015) conducted a study aimed at identifying the obstacles that prevent e- learning use by faculty members at Menoufia University.

The study concluded that there are some obstacles that face faculty members' use of eLearning management systems, such as obstacles related to university management, awareness of faculty members with e-learning, obstacles related to competencies and skills required for using the system and other obstacles. Al-Omari (2015) carried out a study aimed at uncovering the reasons for the reluctance of the teaching staff to use eLearning system on Yarmouk University website from their point of view. The study found that there are many obstacles faced teaching staff members in their use of e-learning, including: Weak infrastructure along with the necessary material equipment, the learners not possessing the skills to use them, and the great burden on member of the teaching staff.

Research Methodology

The research used descriptive analytical methodology which include quantitative and qualitative. It also involves collections of quantitative information. It involves gathering data that describe events and then organizes the sane. It describes the data collection. It is worth to mention that there are two approaches available for the researcher to use: quantitative and qualitative approaches.

Population and Sampling

Study population represented all teaching staff working at Jordanian universities, random sample was selected amounting (372) teaching staff members.

Research Instrument

Self-administrated questionnaire was designed according to research objectives and research questions for the purpose of obtaining the needed data. The questionnaire consists of three parts: the covering letter in which research objectives were explained, subjects were asked to answer all questions accurately. The second part

consists of questions related to demographic data. The third part included the statements that measure research questions. The questionnaire was designed in a five-point Likert scale.

Data collection methods

Two data collection methods are available: Secondary data collection which was used for the purpose of obtaining basic information regarding the research topic that helped to provide the reader with different ideas related to the subject and for setting up questions for discussions on primary data collection. Books, periodicals, journals, references and the internet were used for collecting the required data. The questionnaire was used to collect the primary data from the study sample's subjects.

Instrument Validity

Validity is the degree that testing can assess what the research is trying to assess. The questionnaire was subject to validation by number of university staff. Their comments and amendments were taken in consideration.

Instrument Reliability

Reliability is used to measure the variables included in the questionnaire by calculating the value of the Cronbach Alpha coefficient, where the result is statistically acceptable if its value is more than (0.60), and whenever the value approaches one (1) i.e., 100%, this indicates higher levels of reliability. Alpha Cronbach value was (0.92), so the instrument can be described with consistency, and that the data obtained through it are suitable for measuring variables, and are subject to a high degree of reliability

Data Analysis

All collected data were coded and then analyzed by using Statistical Package of the Social Sciences (SPSS) the following statistical analysis was used:

1. Descriptive statistics were used for the purpose of obtaining frequencies, percent of demographic variables.
2. Central tendency Measures (means and standard deviations) for sample's responses on the questionnaire statements.
3. Furthermore, a (t – test) was used to find the influence of independents variable on the dependent variables

Descriptive Analysis

In terms of sample's demographic data (gender, age, academic rank, and years of experience), the data analysis for the information collected by the self-administered questionnaire revealed the results represented in table (1).

Table (1)
Sample distribution according to Demographic information

Variables	Options	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Male	272	73.1
	Female	100	26.9
Age	Less than 25	45	12.1
	25 to less than 35	105	28.2
	35 to less than 45	115	30.9
	45+	107	28.8
Academic Rank	Teacher	27	7.3
	Assistant prof	192	51.6
	Associated prof.	98	26.3
	Full prof	55	14.8
Experience	Less than 5 years	112	30.1
	5 to less than 10 years	145	39.0
	10 to less than 15	93	25.0
	15+	22	5.9

Table (1) indicates that out of 372 subject, 272 are males that is 73.1% where as 100 are females that is 26.9%. As for respondents' age, the sample was distributed in four categories 12.1% are less than 25 years old, 28.2% fall in the range 25 to less than 35 years old, 30.9% their age ranged between 35 to less than 45 years old, and 28.8% are 45 years old and more. With respect to academic rank, 7.3% of sample's respondents are teachers, 51.6% are assistant Profs, 26.3% are associated Profs, 14.8% are full professors. As for experience, 30.1% of the sample's respondents have less than 5 years of experience, 39.0% have between 5 to less than 10 years of experience, 25% have between 10 to less than 15 years, and 5.9% have 15 or more years of experience.

Research Questions Testing

Q1- To what extent eLearning approach improves the learning process from Jordanian Universities teaching staff Perspectives

Table (2)

Means and standard deviations of sample's responses regarding E-learning improves learning process

No.	Question	Mean	S.D.	Rank	Level	T	Sig
1	eLearning approach provides an interactive system for students' interaction with academicsubjects	3.86	.893	3	High	18.632	0.000
2	Flexibility provided by eLearning approach is important tome	3.68	.973	8	High	13.487	0.000
3	Students interact with eLearning approach in an activeand exciting way	3.63	.966	9	Medium	12.607	0.000
4	eLearning approach provides more educational references and resources than traditionaleducation	3.97	.830	1	High	22.487	0.000
5	eLearning approach that I use isreliable for teaching	3.57	1.055	10	Medium	10.365	0.000
6	eLearning approach can provide face-to-face interaction:	2.37	1.028	15	Medium	-11.900	0.000
7	Learning process can be managed appropriately through e-learning platforms	3.84	.914	4	High	17.764	0.000
8	eLearning approach facilitates the presentation of content in interactive ways:	3.77	.845	7	High	17.495	0.000
9	Education according to eLearning approach provides enthusiasm and desire among students:	2.79	1.160	12	Medium	-3.485	0.000
10	eLearning approach makes it easier for students outside Jordan to access the offered courses	3.52	1.047	11	Medium	9.505	0.000
11	eLearning approach achieves more positive social interaction than traditional teaching	2.50	1.088	13	Medium	-8.865	0.000
12	Evaluation methods according to eLearning approach have the two attributes of honesty and objectivity	3.84	.879	5	High	18.511	0.000
13	Teaching according to eLearning approach develops positive attitudes among students towards the learning process	3.83	.856	6	High	18.783	0.000
14	eLearning approach provides variety of teaching methods, including pictures, videos, and others	3.96	.929	2	High	19.918	0.000

15	eLearning approach takes into account the individual differences of students	2.38	1.028	14	Medium	-11.550	0.000
	Grand Mean	3.43	.446		Medium	18.759	0.000

Table (2) indicates that means of sample responses regarding statements that measure e-learning improves learning process ranged between (2.37- 3.97). The results indicate medium to high sample agreement on all statements that measure eLearning improves learning process. Furthermore, it can be noticed that statement no.4 “eLearning approach provides more educational references and resources than traditional education” “ranked the first, while statement no 4. Which states “eLearning approach can provide face-to-face interaction “ranked the last. All statements are significant.

Moreover, the grand mean (3.43) also confirms the findings, which indicate the sample agreement on the items that measure the impact of eLearning on improving learning process. These findings indicate that study sample agreed that e-learning improves learning process.

Q2- To what extent do universities teaching staff members accept e-learning approach in light of Corona pandemic?

Means and standards deviation and t values were calculated for each statement as shown in table below

Table (3)

Means and standard deviations of sample's responses regarding universities teaching staff members acceptance of eLearning approach in light of Corona pandemic

No	Question	Mean	S.D.	Rank	Level	T	Sig
16	Teaching according to eLearning approach, develops teacher's development and creativity through my review to additional resources	3.72	0.850	5	High	16.233	0.000
17	According to eLearning approach, It is rare for teacher to face technical problems that hinder his teaching	3.79	0.919	2	High	16.650	0.000
18	Preparing com lessons needs less time than traditional one	3.84	0.816	1	High	19.762	0.000
19	Teaching process according to eLearning approach needs many resources and references	3.66	0.902	6	Medium	14.023	0.000
20	I feel satisfied with the availability of means of communication and interaction with students in eLearning approach	3.78	0.862	3	High	17.513	0.000
21	I provide better information to my students through the eLearning approach about their performance in the course:	3.78	0.844	4	High	17.747	0.000
22	I feel satisfied when I use eLearning approach compared to traditional methods	2.71	1.136	10	Medium	-4.930	0.000
23	Teaching according to eLearning approach needs great efforts	3.64	0.951	8	Medium	13.032	0.000
24	I am looking forward to teach the course through eLearning approach	3.58	0.950	9	Medium	11.735	0.000

25	The eLearning approach facilitates the communication mechanism between the teacher and his students	3.65	0.947	7	Medium	13.192	0.000
	Grand Mean	3.61	0.571		Medium	20.728	0.000

Table (3) shows means of sample subjects' responses on statements that universities teaching staff members accept eLearning approach in light of Corona pandemic ranged between (2.71) and (3.84). Table (3) also indicates that respondent's agreement is of medium to high level. Furthermore, statement number (18) "Preparing computerized lessons needs less time than traditional one" ranked the first with a mean of (3.84) and statement number (22) "I feel satisfied when I use eLearning approach compared to traditional methods" ranked the last with a mean of (2.71).

The grand mean (3.61) indicates medium level of agreement, regarding university teaching staff members acceptance of eLearning approach in light of Corona pandemic. The results indicate their acceptance of eLearning approach in light of Corona pandemic

Q3- Do Universities teaching staff members acceptance of eLearning approach in the light of Corona pandemic system differs according to (gender, age, academic rank, and years of experience?)

Table (4)
Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	4.617 ^a	4	1.154	3.641	.006
Intercept	469.299	1	469.299	1480.138	.000
Gender	.702	1	.702	2.214	.138
Age	.802	1	.802	2.530	.113
Academic Rank	.151	1	.151	.477	.490
Experience	.017	1	.017	.054	.816
Error	116.363	367	.317		
Total	4978.890	372			
Corrected Total	120.980	371			

Table (4) indicates that there are no differences in universities teaching staff members acceptance of eLearning approach in the light of Corona pandemic system according to their (gender, age, academic rank, years of experience).

Discussion

The current study has found the e-learning an acceptable method in education according to instructors' perspective. The instructors exhibit a high level of perception toward the e-learning in the most of the items used instrument. The items that show less level of perception were about the student's interaction and student-instructor interaction. The new e-learning environments make the communication more difficult and dissatisfied in term of e-learning environment. The environment interaction is one of e-learning limitation.

The instructors show medium level of satisfaction toward e-learning environment and was in the last rank of response ration. Instructor satisfaction is an important part in education. The possible explanation is the instructors give more effort in e-learning. Furthermore, the e-learning was associated with high level of stress and anxiety for both students and instructors. Therefore, there is a need for interventions target the instructor satisfaction in the time of COVID-19 pandemic.

There was no significant difference between instructors' perspective toward e-learning in term of demographic variable as age, and gender. Academic rank and years of experience were not a significant factor of perspective toward e-learning environment. The academic rank and year of experience has not a clear impact on instructors' perspective due to e-learning was not practiced enough in Jordanian high education institutions before COVID-19 pandemic. The current experience of COVID-19 pandemic will facilitate the future trend toward the e-learning and blinded learning even after this pandemic.

Conclusion and recommendation

The study found that the e-learning is an acceptable education method. Based on the above analysis the study concluded that e-learning improves the learning process, the sample agreement level ranged between medium to high level. The study also concluded that universities teaching staff members accept eLearning approach in light of Corona pandemic. Further improvement and training in different e-learning methods and technologies are required in order to improve the e-learning experience and outcomes. As the instructors' satisfaction was in the last rank, there is a need to interventions for improve instructors' satisfaction.

There are no differences in universities teaching staff members acceptance of e-Learning approach in the light of Corona pandemic system according to their (gender, age, academic rank, years of experience). The study suggested that universities in Jordan either public or private ones should pay attention to the need of e-learning and its effective role in learning process. Since eLearning and its means will be common for the purpose of providing learner with new skills. Universities have to qualify the teaching staff members to be involved in e-learning age through intensive training programs and they are requested to set an e-learning plans.

References

- Adedoyin, O and Soykan, E. (2020). Covid-19 pandemic and online learning: the challenges and opportunities, *Interactive Learning Environments*, DOI:10.1080/10494820.2020.1813180 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2020.1813180>
- Akour, A., Al-Tammemi, A., Barakat, M., Kanj, R., Fakhouri, H., Malkawi, A., Musleh, G. (2020). The Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic and Emergency Distance Teaching on the Psychological Status of University Teachers: A Cross-Sectional Study in Jordan. *The American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, doi:10.4269/ajtmh.20-0877. <https://www.ajtmh.org/view/journals/tpmd/103/6/article-p2391.xml>
- Al Hawamdeh, M (2011). Barriers to the use of e-learning from the viewpoint of faculty members at Al-Balqa Applied University. *Damascus University for Educational Sciences Journal*, 27, 831 - 803, (2 + 1)
- Al Omari, M. (2014.) E-learning and its modern technologies. Publications of the Deanship of Scientific Research and Postgraduate Studies, Yarmouk University.
- Al-Hajaya, M. (2010.) The reality of e-learning in Jordanian universities. A scientific paper presented to the third international conference on e-learning entitled: "The role of e-learning in enhancing knowledge societies" organized by the Zain E-Learning Center at the University of Bahrain from 6-8 / 4/2010
- Al-Mazari, S... (2014). The availability degree of competencies of the electronic learning management system »MOODLE» among the faculty members of the proposed Arab University / Jordan branch from their point of view (Master Thesis). Yarmouk University.
- Alqahtani, M. (2011). An investigation into the language needs of Saudi students studying in British postgraduate programmed and the cultural differences impacting on them (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). University of Southampton, Southampton, UK.
- Amarin N., (2020), The Art of Teaching in Fusion Classroom Learning Situations. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 14(11).
- Amarin N., Al-Saleh A., (2020), The Effect of Color Use in Designing Instructional Aids on Learners' Academic Performance. *Journal of E-Learning and Knowledge Society*, 16(2), 42-50. <https://doi.org/10.20368/1971-8829/1135246>
- Arnou, C. (2020). Scenario's vooronderwijstijdensenna de corona-crisis. Retrieved, April 20, 2020, from <https://ppw.kuleuven.be/platform/Blogs/scenario2019s-voor-onderwijs-tijdens-en-nade-corona-crisis>.
- Badawi, M. (2015). Barriers to the use of university faculty members Menoufia Electronic Learning Management Systems (LMS) from their point of view. *Research Journal Educational and Psychological*, 30, 4, 46- , 69
- Benaichi Bachir and Benaichi Ammar (2018) The Reality of the Application of the E-Education in Algerian Universities: Case Study in the University of Biskra
- Bozkurt, A., & Sharma, R. C. (2020). Emergency remote teaching in a time of global crisis due to Corona Virus pandemic. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(1), i-iv.
- De-Marcos, L. (2016). On the effectiveness of game-like and social approaches in learning: Comparing educational gaming, gamification and social networks. *Computers and Education*, 95, 99-113.
- De-Marcos, L. (2016). On the effectiveness of game-like and social approaches in learning: Comparing educational gaming, gamification and social networks. *Computers and Education*, 95, 99-113.
- Halas, F. (2018) Effect of Computerized Examinations Quality on the Acceptance of Faculty Members in Palestinian Universities to Work on This Type of Examinations (Case study - Islamic University of Gaza), MSc, - Islamic University of Gaza

- Hofmeister, Christian. Pilz, Matthias (2020). Using E-Learning to Deliver In-Service Teacher Training in the Vocational Education Sector: Perception and Acceptance in Poland, Italy and Germany, 10(7), <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci10070182>
- Mazroua, Y (2013). Attitudes of faculty members at King UniversityKhaled towards using the blackboard eLearning management system. *Journal of the Educational Society.*- 84-114 ,(52) *Social Studies*,
- Nur, N., Fazyudi, A., &Kamaro, B. (2014) A study on the student's perspective on the effectiveness of using e-learning, *Social and Behavioral Sciences* 123, pp 139 – 144
- Randy, G. (2011). E-learning in the 21st century. A framework for research and practice, 2, 110–111.
- Rodrigues ,H, Filomena, A.Vanessa., F &Sara, L.(2019) Tracking e-learning through published papers: A systematic review , *Computers &Education*Volume 136, , Pages 87-98
- Sulaiman, M. (2014). The effectiveness of training on the use of the learning management system and Electronic content in developing information awareness and e-learning skills Faculty members at Taibah University. *Journal of the College of Education in Zagazig*83, (127-190).
- Titie, P. Suthathip, S., Pornpimol, C. &Thepcha, S., (2018) Effectivness of Learning Design and affecting Variabless in Thai Public Schools *Malaysian Journal of Learning and Instruction: Vol. 15 (No. 1) pp: 1-34*
- Tshabalala, M., Ndeya-Ndereya, C. & Merwe, T. (2014). Implementing Blended Learning at a Developing University: Obstacles in the Way *Electronic Journal of e-Learning*, 1 (12), 101-110.

Author Information

Nidal ZakiAmarin

Faculty of Arts
Al-Zaytoonah University of Jordan, Jordan

Tarik Faris Al Soub

Faculty of Arts and Sciences
Aqaba University of Technology, Jordan
